

Electrochemical formation and corrosion studies on zinc-nickel alloys^ψ

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Electrochemical formation of zinc-nickel alloy films has been investigated with the object of determination of their ability to withstand corrosion. Both potentiostatic and galvanostatic techniques were used for the preparation of the alloy films. Polarization and impedance measurements; and Tafel studies were carried out for the estimation of their corrosion resistance. Non-metallic inclusions during electrochemical formation of nickel-zinc alloys have also been carried out to explore possibilities of obtaining alloy films endowed with improved electrochemical corrosion resistance.

Alloys have been developed and are used because they have properties that are not obtainable with pure metals. In some situations of practical interest electrodeposition offers possibility of formation of alloys endowed with desired mechanical strength and resistance towards electrochemical corrosion¹⁻³. We present herein our work dealing with electrochemical formation of zinc-nickel alloy systems of contemporary relevance to investigate their ability to withstand impairment due to electrochemical corrosion.

Zinc-nickel alloys for possible applications as protective coatings have been extensively studied. Their resistance towards corrosion depends on structure and composition, in addition to the electrochemical conditions under which their preparation is carried out^{4,5}. We have undertaken preparation of the zinc-nickel alloys of variable composition to investigate their corrosion characteristics in order to identify situations in which formation of the alloys with enhanced corrosion resistance may become possible. Possibilities of further improvement in their corrosion characteristics by non-metallic inclusions has also been explored. Corrosion behaviour of electrochemically formed nickel-zinc alloy coatings (i) in the presence of surface active material during electrodeposition and (ii) in the presence of inhibitors in the corrosive electrolyte has been investigated. Their electrochemical formation and characterization in the presence of non-metallic inclusions has also been studied. Both potentiostatic and galvanostatic electrodeposition techniques were used for the preparation of alloy films. Tafel plot, electrochemical impedance and polarization resistance methods were used for the determination of corrosion rates of variously formed zinc-nickel alloys.

Experimental

Analytical grade nickel sulphate and zinc sulphate were used for the preparation of all electroplating solutions in distilled water. For electrodeposition of all alloy films, a three electrode set-up containing working, counter and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used. Working as well as counter electrodes were cleaned with emery papers, polished with METSES fluid (MMSPL, Chennai) and washed successively with acetone and distilled water. All electrochemical preparations were carried out under controlled continuous stirring. Digital multimeters (Systronics 445 and HIL 2161) were used for measurement of the deposition potential and the current flowing between the working and counter electrodes respectively. Galvanostatic depositions were carried out using constant current power supply (Lake shore 120, USA).

For the estimation of corrosion characteristics of the electrodeposited alloys, Tafel plots, impedance and polarization resistance measurements were used. Acquisition and analysis of the data were carried out using Electrochemical Measurement System, Model 378 (EG & G, PARC, USA) consisting of model 273 potentiostat/galvanostat and a lock-in Amplifier (5208) in conjunction with an IBM personal computer and printer (EPSON).

Results and discussion

Electrodeposition of alloys from aqueous solutions is possible only when the deposition potential of ionic species to be discharged have identical deposition potentials⁶. If the deposition potentials of the ions are far apart then these deposition potentials can be brought closer for simultaneous deposition of ions either by adjusting the ratio of

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

ionic concentrations of the constituents in the electroplating bath, or by the use of complex ions in the electroplating bath⁷. Simultaneous discharge of ions can also be achieved using the limiting current⁸.

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Zinc and nickel differ considerably in their deposition potentials in ordinary solutions. However, if deposition is attempted at a potential beyond the deposition potential of the more electropositive ion, both the ions may discharge together⁷. Current-voltage behaviour of a mixture of zinc sulphate and nickel sulphate using titanium electrodes shown in Fig. 1 indicates possibility of simultaneous deposition in the range -0.50 to -0.70 V vs SCE. In all subse-

Fig. 1. A typical current-voltage curve.

quent studies alloy formation was carried out at a potential of -0.70 V vs SCE. Estimation of composition of the electrodeposits was carried out using the procedure reported elsewhere⁹. The rates of deposition of the alloy constituents are related as

$$\frac{R_{Zn}}{R_{Ni}} = \frac{D_{Zn^{2+}}(1 - t_{Ni^{2+}})}{D_{Ni^{2+}}(1 - t_{Zn^{2+}})} \times \frac{C_{Zn^{2+}}}{C_{Ni^{2+}}} \quad (1)$$

This relationship assumes formation of depletion layer of identical thickness for both the ions in the interfacial region during electrolysis. Transport numbers were calculated using the relationship

$$t_i = \frac{C_i Z_i \lambda_i}{\sum C_i Z_i \lambda_i} \quad (2)$$

where C_i , Z_i and λ_i denotes concentration, charge and equivalent ionic conductivity respectively.

The diffusion coefficients were calculated using the equation¹⁰

$$D_i = \frac{RT}{Z_i F^2} \cdot \lambda_i \quad (3)$$

The symbols have their usual significance. The estimated alloy compositions alongwith transport numbers are included in Table 1. Zn is seen to deposit somewhat in excess of its concentration in the electroplating solution inspite of its deposition potential being greater than that for nickel. This obviously occurs due to relatively sluggish movement of Ni^{2+} ion in the depletion layer indicated by its relatively small magnitude of diffusion coefficient and transport number.

Table 1. Transport number and composition of Zn-Ni alloys

Deposition potential = -0.70 V vs SCE

Solution no.	Electroplating solution composition		$t_{Zn^{2+}}$	$t_{Ni^{2+}}$	Alloy composition	
	ZnSO ₄ (M)	NiSO ₄ (M)			Zn	Ni
1	1.0	0.01	0.393	0.004	1.0	0.005
2	1.0	0.05	0.379	0.018	1.0	0.029
3	1.0	0.10	0.362	0.034	1.0	0.062
4	1.0	0.15	0.346	0.049	1.0	0.098
5	1.0	0.20	0.332	0.062	1.0	0.134

In order to investigate the electrochemical corrosion behaviour of the prepared alloy films, variation of current with potential was studied to obtain Tafel plots as shown in Fig. 2. The anodic and cathodic Tafel plots are described by

$$\eta = \beta \log \frac{i}{i_{corr}} \quad (4)$$

where η = over voltage; i = current at the applied potential and i_{corr} = corrosion current. The i_{corr} values were obtained by the intersection of anodic and cathodic Tafel curves at E_{corr} ($I=0$). The corrosion rates were then estimated using the relationship¹¹

$$R_{corr}(\text{mpy}) = \frac{0.13 \times i_{corr} \times (E.W.)}{d.A.} \quad (5)$$

(E.W.) denotes equivalent weight of the electroactive mate-

rial; A , the cross-sectional area of the electroactive material; d its density and mpy, milliinch per year.

Fig. 2. A representative Tafel plot.

The corrosion rates alongwith the corrosion current values of alloy films are summarized in Table 2. The alloy films prepared from electroplating solution richer in nickel (15% and 20% Ni²⁺) exhibit enhanced corrosion contrary to expectations based on higher nobility of nickel. This may be attributed to the structural heterogeneity at the microscopic level during the formation of alloys as well as to the formation of intermetallic compounds¹².

Electrochemical formation and corrosion studies on Ni-Zn alloys :

Electrochemical deposition of Ni-Zn alloy films from the electroplating solutions containing different concentration of ZnSO₄ and a fixed concentration of NiSO₄ was also

Table 2. Electrochemical corrosion parameters of Zn-Ni alloy films

Testing electrolyte = 3% NaCl

Solution no.	Electroplating solution composition		i_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	R_{corr} (mpy)
	ZnSO ₄ (M)	NiSO ₄ (M)		
1	1.0	0.01	1.06	1.30
2	1.0	0.05	0.37	0.44
3	1.0	0.10	1.55	1.90
4	1.0	0.15	8.20	9.90
5	1.0	0.20	5.61	8.00

attempted. During deposition of the alloy films, current initially decreases and subsequently attains a steady state value (Fig. 3). The thickness of the prepared alloy films included in Table 3 was calculated using the expression¹³

$$F_T = \frac{i \times t \times (E.W.)}{F \times d \times A} \quad (6)$$

where i = deposition current, t = time of deposition. Other symbols have their usual meaning.

Fig. 3. Variation of current with time during potentiostatic deposition of alloy film.

Table 3. Electrodeposition condition, film thickness and corrosion parameters of Ni-Zn alloys

Deposition potential = -0.90 V vs SCE, deposition time = 30 min, testing electrolyte = 5% NaCl solution, working electrode area = 0.20 cm²

no.	Electroplating solution composition		Film thickness $\times 10^3$	i_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	R_{corr} (g/sec) $\times 10^8$
	ZnSO ₄ (M)	NiSO ₄ (M)			
1	0.50	0.10	6.70	170.2	10.74
2	0.50	0.15	9.20	193.0	12.70
3	0.50	0.20	7.11	130.8	8.40
4	0.50	0.25	7.06	124.0	7.97

Prepared alloy films were subjected to impedance spectral studies. A representative plot is given in Fig. 4. The alloy bearing electrode was treated analogous to a Randell cell¹⁴ to obtain the polarization resistance values. Corrosion currents and corrosion rates obtained using the expressions^{15,11}

$$i_{corr} = \frac{RT}{F} \cdot \frac{1}{R_p} \quad (7)$$

and

$$R_{\text{corr}} (\text{g/sec}) = \frac{i_{\text{corr}} \times (E.W.)}{F} \quad (8)$$

are also included in Table 3. All the Ni-Zn electrodeposits are seen to be endowed with comparable corrosion rates.

Fig. 4. A representative impedance plot.

Ni-Zn alloy films were also prepared under galvanostatic control using different current densities. The alloy films were subjected to impedance spectral studies to obtain the corrosion current and corrosion rates. A reduction in corrosion rate (Table 4) is observed with the increase in current density perhaps due to the formation of finer grained deposits at higher current density¹⁶.

Surface active agents are expected to influence the quality of the deposits as a result of reduction in the potentials of the discharging metal ions. Accordingly we prepared Ni-Zn alloy films galvanostatically using electroplating bath containing varying concentration of the surfactant CPC (cetyl pyridinium chloride). Prepared alloy films were subjected to anodic polarization for the determination of the polarization resistance value, R_p . Corrosion current and corrosion rates alongwith the R_p values summarized in Table

Table 4. Corrosion characteristics of galvanostatically deposited Ni-Zn alloys

Electroplating solution composition = 0.50 M NiSO₄ + 0.20 M ZnSO₄, deposition time = 30 min, testing electrolyte = 5% NaCl

Current density (mA/cm ²)	i_{corr} (mA/cm ²)	R_{corr} (g/sec) × 10 ⁸
-0.50	130.2	8.36
	140.0	8.99
-1.00	101.7	6.53
	106.7	6.86
-1.50	75.9	4.88
	77.4	4.97

5 reveal a significant reduction in corrosion with the increase concentration of the surfactant in the electroplating solution. The adsorption of surfactant molecules on the electroactive sites of electrode surface seems responsible for the observed reduction in corrosion¹⁷.

Electrodeposition and corrosion studies on non-metal containing Ni-Zn alloys :

Incorporation of non-metals often results in deposits of improved corrosion resistance. Attempts have been made to deposit Ni-Zn alloy films electrochemically from the electroplating solutions having fixed concentration of Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺ ions and varying concentration of phosphorous as sodium hypophosphite. These alloys were prepared at a potential of -1.00 V vs SCE in the light of the potential domain (upto -1.10 V vs SCE) identified on the basis of current-voltage studies. Corrosion rates included in Table 6 alongwith the other parameters were estimated using the expressions (7) and (8). The R_p values of the alloy films were obtained using impedance spectral studies. It is seen that the alloy films prepared from the electroplating bath containing 0.20 M concentration of sodium hypophosphite show a marked reduction in corrosion. This reduction is attributed to the formation of hypophosphite anion barrier layer between the alloy and electrolyte¹⁸ which in turn pre-

Table 5. Corrosion characteristics of Ni-Zn alloys prepared galvanostatically in presence of surfactant

Deposition current density = -0.50 mA/cm², deposition time = 30 min, testing electrolyte solution = 5% NaCl, working area of electrode = 0.20 cm²

Electroplating solution composition			R_p	i_{corr}	R_{corr}
NiSO ₄ (M)	ZnSO ₄ (M)	CPC*(mM)	(Ω)	(μA/cm ²)	(g/sec) × 10 ⁸
0.50	0.20	0.00	239.42	535.9	34.43
0.50	0.20	0.25	526.31	243.8	15.66
0.50	0.20	0.50	952.38	134.7	8.66
0.50	0.20	0.75	1666.66	77.0	4.95
0.50	0.20	1.00	2804.89	45.7	2.94

* CPC = Cetyl pyridinium chloride.

Table 6. Deposition conditions, film thickness values and characteristic corrosion parameters of phosphorous containing Ni-Zn alloy filmsDeposition potential = -1.00 V vs SCE, deposition time = 30 min, testing electrolyte solution = 5% NaCl, working area of electrode = 0.20 cm²

Solution no.	Electroplating solution composition			Film thickness (cm × 10 ³)	<i>i</i> _{corr} (μA/cm ²)	<i>R</i> _{corr} (g/sec) × 10 ⁹
	NiSO ₄ (M)	ZnSO ₄ (M)	NaH ₂ PO ₂ (M)			
1	0.50	0.20	0.00	4.42	130.8	84.00
2	0.50	0.20	0.20	1.57	9.3	4.92
3	0.50	0.20	0.40	1.38	27.6	14.58
4	0.50	0.20	0.60	1.07	64.4	34.02

Table 7. Electrodeposition conditions, film thickness values and corrosion data of boron containing Ni-Zn alloy filmsDeposition potential = -1.05 V vs SCE, deposition time = 30 min, testing electrolyte solution = 3% NaCl, working area of electrode = 0.20 cm²

Solution no.	Electroplating solution composition			Film thickness (cm × 10 ⁴)	<i>i</i> _{corr} (μA/cm ²)	<i>R</i> _{corr} (g/sec) × 10 ⁸
	NiSO ₄ (M)	ZnSO ₄ (M)	B(OH) ₃			
1	0.50	0.20	0.00	44.2	130.8	8.40
2	0.50	0.20	0.10	2.3	76.9	3.51
3	0.50	0.20	0.20	4.2	111.2	6.12
4	0.50	0.20	0.30	5.2	136.9	6.24
5	0.50	0.20	0.40	5.0	93.3	4.25

vents Ni dissolution. The inclusion of phosphorous may occur as¹²

Boron which may act as a complexing agent is also expected to improve the corrosion behaviour of Ni-Zn alloy films. We have deposited boron containing Ni-Zn alloys from the electroplating solutions having fixed concentration of NiSO₄ and ZnSO₄ and varying concentration of boric acid at a potential of -1.05 V vs SCE. The deposition potential is chosen on the basis of current-voltage behaviour of the electroplating solutions. The deposited alloys were subjected to polarization resistance study (Fig. 5) to obtain *R*_p values. Corrosion currents, corrosion rates and film thickness values estimated using expressions (7), (8) and (6) respectively are summarized in Table 7. It is found that the inclusion of boron is possible and deposits obtained from electroplating solution containing 20% boron show considerably enhanced corrosion resistance. Boric acid dissociation resulting in the formation of a complex with the Ni according to the reaction¹⁹

is believed to be responsible for the observed enhanced corrosion resistance.

Corrosion study of electrodeposited Ni-Zn alloys in presence of inhibitors :

Fig. 5. Polarization behaviour of a representative nickel-zinc alloy film.

Inhibitors play an important role in the containment of corrosion of alloys through adsorption. We have studied the corrosion behaviour of electrodeposited Ni-Zn alloys in presence of ethanolic solutions of inhibitors di-propyl ether (CH₃CH₂CH)₂O and di-propyl sulphide (CH₃CH₂CH)₂S. Surface tension measurements were carried out to obtain their CMC values. Corrosion currents

Table 8. Characteristic corrosion parameters of Ni-Zn alloy without and with the inhibitor dipropyl ether [(CH₃CH₂CH₂)₂O]Electroplating solution composition = 0.50 M NiSO₄ + 0.20 M ZnSO₄

Testing solution composition		R_p	i_{corr}	R_{corr}	(% Inhib.
NaCl (M)	(CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ O (M)	(Ω)	(μA/cm ²)	(g/sec) × 10 ⁸	
0.50	0.000	288.46	445.0	28.59	00.0
0.50	0.025	625.00	205.5	13.20	53.8
0.50	0.050	714.29	179.5	11.53	59.7
0.50	0.075	833.33	154.0	9.89	65.4
0.50	0.100	937.50	137.0	8.80	69.2
0.50	0.125	1062.00	120.8	7.76	72.9

Table 9. Electrochemical corrosion characteristics of Ni-Zn alloy without and with the inhibitor di-propyl sulphide [(CH₃CH₂CH₂)₂S]Electroplating bath composition = 0.50 M NiSO₄ + 0.20 M ZnSO₄

Testing solution composition		R_p	i_{corr}	R_{corr}	(% Inhib.
NaCl (M)	(CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ S (M)	(Ω)	(μA/cm ²)	(g/sec) × 10 ⁹	
0.50	0.000	470.58	272.5	17.50	00.0
0.50	0.025	645.16	199.0	12.80	27.0
0.50	0.050	740.74	173.0	11.15	36.5
0.50	0.075	869.56	147.5	9.50	45.9
0.50	0.100	1000.00	128.5	8.25	52.8

obtained from anodic polarization studies were used for the estimation of corrosion inhibition using the expression²⁰

$$(\%) I_{inhb} = \left(1 - \frac{i'_{corr}}{i_{corr}}\right) \times 100 \quad (11)$$

i_{corr} and i'_{corr} , the corrosion currents without and with the inhibitors, and % (I_{inhb}), the percentage inhibition values are summarized in Tables 8 and 9 respectively. Maximum inhibitions were observed at CMC values of the inhibitors. This obviously arises on account of adsorption of the inhibitor molecules which blocks the reaction sites and offers physical barriers to the diffusion of corroding species towards the electrode surface²¹.

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